

ABOUT THE OBSERVED PROGRESS OF A MOVING CLOCK

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Annotation

The question of the observed course of a moving clock is considered. It is proved that the observed readings of clocks moving towards the observer go faster than the observed readings of stationary clocks. The results of experimental confirmation of this conclusion are presented. A popular scientific presentation of the proof of the acceleration of the observed course of a clock moving towards the observer is given. In the special theory of relativity (SRT), the exact opposite conclusion is made: in accordance with SRT, clocks moving towards the observer, according to observations, go slower than stationary ones. This indicates that there is an error in the SRT.

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1. Introduction

In 2022, a group of 100 scientists and engineers in St. Petersburg conducted an experiment during which they directly observed the readings of clocks located on aircraft during their flight [1-4]. The experiment was carried out using a high-precision radar.

According to the “International Register of Achievements and Records,” the work [2] received the title “Property of the Nation.” The corresponding certificate “The largest scientific team of authors refuting the special theory of relativity” was received, which is awarded to the “scientific team for conducting the experiment” [5].

This experiment received media coverage [6-10].

During the experiment, it was established with a high confidence probability that at speeds of 83-240 m/s, the observed readings of a moving clock when moving towards an observer (radar) go faster than a stationary clock, and when moving away from the observer - slower than a stationary clock.

The results of this experiment contradict the provisions of the special theory of relativity (SRT), according to which moving clocks, according to their observed readings, in all cases (it should be emphasized that also in the case of a clock approaching the observer) go slower than a stationary clock.

This work examines the theoretical aspects of the effect of acceleration and deceleration of the observed rate of a clock as it moves towards or away from the observer.

2. Preliminary remarks and definitions

Let's consider an inertial reference system (ISR) with an infinite set of motionless clocks synchronized with each other in advance, next to which there are motionless observers.

Let to the origin uniformly and rectilinearly along the X axis a clock is moving that is synchronized with a fixed ISO clock. The fact of synchronization of moving clocks with stationary

clocks can be verified by any stationary observer at the moment when the moving clock passes in close proximity to him. At this moment, the moving clock and the stationary clock that happened to be nearby show the same time to the observer next to them.

Let us call the true readings of a moving clock their readings to observers who happen to be in close proximity at the moment the clock passes next to them. But since all stationary ISO clocks are synchronized, and moving clocks are synchronized with all ISO clocks, the true readings of a moving clock are no different from the readings of any stationary clock to an observer located next to them. In other words, the true readings of a moving clock are nothing more than the readings of a stationary ISO clock, which is recorded by an observer located next to them (provided that the moving clock is synchronized with the ISO clock).

Conclusion. The true readings of clocks moving in ISO, provided they are synchronized with all ISO clocks at any time, are equal to the readings of stationary clocks, which are recorded by an observer located next to them.

In this work, we will use the following terms.

The course of the clock . The progress of the clock.

The true course of the clock . The course of the true readings of the clock, which is fixed by an observer located next to the clock.

Observed clock progress . The progress of the observed clock readings, which is recorded by a remote observer.

Observed time . observable clock progress (clock readings).

True time . The true progress of the clock (clock readings).

3. Derivation of formulas proving the fact of acceleration of the observed rate of clocks that move towards the observer, as well as the fact of deceleration of the observed rate of clocks when they move from the observer

Let the observer at the origin of the ISO coordinates monitor the readings of a clock moving towards him. Since the observed readings of a moving clock arrive at the observer with a delay equal to the time of movement of electromagnetic waves (a ray of light) from the clock to the observer, the observed reading of a moving clock t_{obs} can be determined by the formula

$$t_{obs} = t_{tr} - \Delta t_{del} = t_{tr} - \frac{r_{obs}}{c}, \quad (1)$$

where t_{tr} is the true reading of the moving clock at the moment of its observation;

Δt_{del} – the delay time for the receipt of readings from a remote clock to the observer, equal to the time of movement of electromagnetic waves from the clock to the observer;

r_{obs} – the distance from the observer to the clock at the moment of emission of electromagnetic waves through which observation is carried out.

Consider the following example. Let the moving clocks be monitored using ADS -B automatic dependent surveillance technology. In this case, next to the clock there is an ADS -B transmitter (transponder), which once a second (or more often) broadcasts messages containing the coordinates of the moving clock and the exact time of the moment the message was broadcast. At the origin there is an ADS -B receiver that receives ADS -B messages and provides the observer with information about the moving clock on the ADS -B display: the received coordinates of the moving clock, as well as their readings.

The distance from the ADS -B receiver to the clock, calculated from the transmitted coordinates (at the time the ADS -B message was received) is the value of the observed distance to the clock r_{obs} :

$$r_{obs} = \sqrt{x_{ADS}^2 + y_{ADS}^2 + z_{ADS}^2},$$

where x_{ADS} , y_{ADS} and z_{ADS} are the clock coordinates in the ADS -B message received by the receiving ADS -B station.

Obviously, the readings of the moving clock displayed on the ADS -B display will lag behind the readings of the stationary clocks next to the display at the origin by the value of the information arrival delay $\Delta t_{del} = r_{obs}/c$.

On the observed course of a moving clock

Let's analyze expression (1) using Fig. 1. This figure shows a clock moving towards the observer at the moment $t_{tr}^1 = 0$ when the true clock readings are zero, and a second later, at the moment $t_{tr}^2 = 1$. At the first moment, the distance from the observer to the clock is equal to r_{obs}^1 , at the second moment, after a second this distance is equal to r_{obs}^2 . $r_{obs}^2 < r_{obs}^1$, this means that the distance to the clock has decreased per second as the clock moves towards the observer.

Fig 1. On the observed course of a moving clock

At the first moment of time, the observed reading of the moving clock in accordance with equation (1) is equal to

$$t_{obs}^1 = 0 - \frac{r_{obs}^1}{c} = -\frac{r_{obs}^1}{c}.$$

At the second moment of time, the observed reading of the moving clock is

$$t_{obs}^2 = 1 - \frac{r_{obs}^2}{c}$$

Let's find the difference between the observed readings of the moving clock at the second and first time:

$$\Delta t_{obs} = 1 - \frac{r_{obs}^2}{c} + \frac{r_{obs}^1}{c} = 1 + \frac{r_{obs}^1 - r_{obs}^2}{c} \quad (2)$$

Expression (2) shows that during a time equal to one second, which passes according to the true readings of a moving clock, according to the observed readings of these clocks,

$$1 + \frac{r_{obs}^1 - r_{obs}^2}{c} \text{ seconds.}$$

And since $r_{obs}^1 > r_{obs}^2$ (the clock moves towards the observer), $r_{obs}^1 - r_{obs}^2 > 0$ then

$$\Delta t_{obs} = 1 + \frac{r_{obs}^1 - r_{obs}^2}{c} > 1.$$

In other words, in one second, according to a stationary clock, more than a second passes according to the observed readings of a moving clock.

This means that the clock moving towards the observer, according to the observed readings, *goes faster than the stationary clock*.

In the case of movement of the clock from the observer in expression (2) $r_{obs}^1 < r_{obs}^2$. In this case

$$\Delta t_{obs} = 1 + \frac{r_{obs}^1 - r_{obs}^2}{c} < 1.$$

This means that clocks moving away from the observer, according to the observed readings, *go slower than stationary clocks*.

Clock synchronization

Suppose we need to determine if the clock O at the origin and the stationary clock are synchronized A , located at a distance r_{obs}^A from the origin.

If the clock coordinates are known (x_A, y_A, z_A), then the distance from the origin of coordinates to clock A is determined by the formula

$$r_{obs}^A = \sqrt{x_A^2 + y_A^2 + z_A^2}.$$

To determine whether clocks O and A are synchronized, the observed readings are obtained from the origin t_{obs}^A hours A and check whether the relation is satisfied

$$t_{obs}^A = t_{tr}^O - \frac{r_{obs}^A}{c}, \quad (3 a)$$

where t_{tr}^O are the true readings of clock O at the origin of coordinates to an observer located next to it at the moment of observing clock A .

If this equality holds, then the clocks of O and A are synchronized.

Equality (3) can be rewritten in another, easier to understand form:

$$t_{obs}^A + \frac{r_{obs}^A}{c} = t_{tr}^O, \quad (3 b)$$

or what is the same

$$t_{tr}^A = t_{tr}^O. \quad (3 c)$$

In other words, checking the synchronization of two clocks O and A comes down to checking the equality of their true readings at the same point in time.

Example . Let it be necessary to determine whether the clock M located on the Moon is synchronized with the earthy clock E . M clock readings are transmitted to Earth using ADS -B technology. At the same time, the messages transmitted from the lunar clock contain data on the time of transmission of messages t_{obs}^M . The ADS-B ground station receiver receives messages and determines the time of reception of messages using the Earth clock t_{tr}^E .

The true time of the lunar clock at the time of receiving the message is determined by the formula (3 b):

$$t_{tr}^M = t_{obs}^M + \frac{r_{obs}^M}{c}.$$

The physical meaning of the magnitude of the lunar clock readings observed from the Earth t_{obs}^M is as follows. Let's imagine that the lunar clock has a huge dial made of LEDs, which we can see on the Moon using ordinary binoculars. The readings that we see when looking at this watch through binoculars represent the value t_{obs}^M (Fig. 2).

Fig 2. When observing a clock with a huge dial on the Moon using binoculars, we will see the observed clock readings. Moonlight travels to Earth in approximately 1.27 seconds. Therefore, the true readings of the lunar clock will be 1.27 s longer than the observed ones

If the Earth clock and the lunar clock are synchronized, then the equality

$$t_{tr}^M = t_{tr}^E.$$

If, for example, the received ADS -B message received data that the message was sent from the lunar clock at zero hours, zero minutes and one second (“00:00:01”), then $t_{obs}^M = 1$ sec. Light travels from the Moon to the Earth in approximately 1.27 seconds. Therefore, the true readings of the lunar clock at the time the message was received are equal to

$$t_{tr}^M = 1 + 1,27 = 2,27 \text{ sec.}$$

If, according to the Earth's clock, the time of receiving the message coincides with this time, that is, $t_{tr}^E = 2,27$ sec, then the clocks of the Earth and the Moon are synchronized.

If the clocks are not synchronized, but it is required to synchronize them, then one of the clocks is adjusted so that equality (3) is satisfied.

Note that in the case of movement of clock A , checking the synchronization of this clock with the clock at the origin is carried out using the same formula (3 c). It should be taken into account that when calculating the true time of clock A using formula (3 b), it is necessary to use the value of the observed distance to the clock r_{obs}^A , which differs from the true distance r_{tr}^A [1, 11, 12].

Derivation of a formula relating the observed and true time intervals counted by a moving clock

ADS -B messages that are transmitted from a moving clock at times t_1 and t_2 , the time interval between these messages is $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1$. At the time of transmission of the first message, the distance to the moving clock was r_1 , so the first message was observed by the observer's clock at the moment of time $t'_1 = t_1 + \frac{r_1}{c}$. Time interval between messages Δt moving clock with speed v will travel a distance $\Delta r = v\Delta t$, and at the time of the transmission of the second message they will be at a distance $r_2 = r_1 - \Delta r = r_1 - v\Delta t$. Therefore, the second message will be observed by the observer at time

$$t'_2 = t_2 + \frac{r_2}{c} = t_2 + \frac{r_1 - v\Delta t}{c}.$$

Let's find the time interval between message observations

$$\Delta t' = t'_2 - t'_1 = t_2 + \frac{r_1 - v\Delta t}{c} - t_1 - \frac{r_1}{c} = t_2 - t_1 - \frac{v\Delta t}{c} = \Delta t \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right).$$

Thus,

$$\Delta t = \frac{\Delta t'}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}.$$

In this expression $\Delta t' = t'_2 - t'_1$, is the time interval elapsed between the moments of observation of ADS -B messages according to the observer's stationary clock; Δt – time interval between messages, which was observed on the ADS -B electronic display. In other words, while the time interval is passing on the observer's watch $\Delta t'$, the time interval Δt is passing on the ADS -B electronic display. Since $\Delta t > \Delta t'$, then the readings of the moving clock on the ADS -B electronic display go faster than the readings of the observer's stationary clock. In one second, seconds (more than a second) pass $\frac{1}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}$ according to the observer's stationary clock on the ADS -B electronic display.

So, we have strictly proven that in one second, according to the observer's stationary clock, the observed readings of the clock moving towards the observer will change by

$$\frac{1}{1 - \frac{v}{c}} \text{ seconds (more than a second).}$$

For example, if the clock moves to the origin at a speed of 0.5 the speed of light, the observed readings of the moving clock will move 2 times faster. That is, in one second according to a stationary clock, two seconds will pass according to the observed readings of a moving clock. With a speed of approach to the origin equal to 0.9 times the speed of light, the readings of a moving clock will move 10 times faster than the readings of a stationary clock; per second according to a stationary clock, according to the observed readings of a moving clock, 10 seconds will pass.

moving **towards the observer**, according to their observed readings, go **faster than** stationary clocks located next to the observer.

Making similar calculations, it is easy to show that in the case of a clock moving away **from the observer**, the observed readings of these clocks are **slower than** the readings of a stationary clock.

In this case, the following relation holds:

$$\Delta t = \frac{\Delta t'}{1 + \frac{v}{c}}.$$

In one second, according to the observer's stationary clock, the observed readings of the clock moving away from the observer will change by

$$\frac{1}{1+\frac{v}{c}} \text{ seconds (less than a second) .}$$

When the speed of the clock is equal to the speed of light, that is, at $v = c$ one second on a stationary clock, according to the observed readings of a moving clock, 0.5 seconds will pass. In this case, the moving clock, according to observations from the origin, will go twice as slow as the stationary clock.

4. Explanation of the effect of accelerating the observed course of a clock moving towards the observer

The effect of accelerating the observed course of a clock moving towards the observer is explained quite simply as follows.

ADS -B messages that contain information about the time of transmission on the air. Using this information, the ADS -B receiver monitors the progress of the clock on the observed object moving towards the observer.

We will assume that messages are transmitted on the air at the beginning of each next second according to a moving clock.

Since the observed object with the clock is moving towards the ADS -B receiver (observer), each subsequent message is transmitted on the air at the moment when the object is closer to the receiver (than at the time of transmission of the previous message). This means that each subsequent message takes less time to “get” to the receiver. This in turn means that messages will arrive at the receiver more often than if the object were stationary. The frequency of arrival of messages about the moment of occurrence of the next second according to the object’s clock will be more than once per second. In other words, the seconds will reportedly alternate more frequently than the seconds of the stationary clock at the origin. An observer at the origin will observe that the clock time of an object moving towards him will run faster than the time according to his own clock.

It is also obvious that when the object with the clock moves away from the receiver, due to the fact that at the moment of transmission of each next message the observed object will be farther than at the moment of transmission of the previous message, messages will arrive at the receiver less often than once per second. In other words, when the observed clock moves away, the observer will note that the observed clock rate has slowed down, the hands of the moving clock will move more slowly than the hands of his stationary clock.

5. SRT about the observed course of a clock moving relative to the observer

In [13, p. 549] says: “Regarding the system K clock (stopwatch whose beats count seconds - approx. Aut.) move at a speed v ; when observed from this frame of reference, not a second, but seconds elapses between the strokes of these clocks $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$, that is, a slightly longer time. The clock, due to its movement, runs slower than at rest.

R. Feynman expressed this position of the SRT about the slow motion of a moving clock as follows: “If you watch from the side as an astronaut (of a moving interplanetary spacecraft - author's note) lights a cigarette, it seems to you that he is doing it more slowly than usual, although he himself he believes that everything is happening at a normal pace. Therefore... instruments for measuring time (“clocks”) must slow down. In other words, when the clock on a spaceship counts

down, in the opinion of the astronaut, 1 second, then in the opinion of an outside observer, $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ a second will pass” [14, p. 272].

A similar position is given in another work: “If you observe a clock from a system in relation to which it moves uniformly at a speed v , it turns out that it moves $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ several times slower than the same clock stationary in relation to this system” [15, p. 156].

It is easy to see that in the SRT Δt_{obs} , the observed time interval calculated from the observed readings of a moving clock and the time interval Δt calculated from a stationary clock are related by the relation:

$$\Delta t_{obs} = \Delta t \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}.$$

In accordance with this, while one second will pass according to the stationary clock, according to the observed readings of the moving (both from the observer and towards the observer) clock,

$$\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \text{ seconds (less than a second).}$$

In accordance with SRT, according to their observed indications, moving clocks always, including *when* the clock approaches the observer (!) go *slower than* stationary clocks.

The reason for the slowdown in the observed readings of a clock moving towards the observer in the SRT is not explained .

6. Experimental confirmation of the effect of acceleration of the observed readings of a clock moving towards the observer

In [2], the results of a practical experiment carried out in St. Petersburg are presented, which refute the position of the special theory of relativity (SRT), according to which moving clocks, due to their movement, in all cases, according to observations, go slower than stationary ones. 48 engineers, 20 graduate students, 24 candidates of sciences, 8 doctors of sciences, 100 people in total took part in the experiment.

An experimental fact established experimentally is that a clock moving towards an observer, according to observations, goes faster than his stationary clock. SRT contradicts this experimental fact. The probability that the STR formula expressing the slowdown of a moving clock is unreliable is greater than 0.9999999999744, that is, practically equal to one. The hypothesis “STR is an erroneous theory”, in accordance with experiment, is practically reliable. It has been experimentally proven that when observing astronauts a spaceship moving towards the observer, their movements and speech will be observed accelerated by a $1/(1 - v/c)$ factor of, where v and c are the speed of the spaceship and the speed of light, respectively. SRT predicts that in this case the astronauts' movements will be observed to be slower by a factor of $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ times, thus the STR predictions contradict experimental data. The experiment was carried out using a monopulse secondary surveillance radar, which provides high-precision measurement of time intervals between the moments of transmitting a request and receiving response signals from aircraft transponders. The practical value of this work lies in the fact that its results will help technical scientists, as well as specialists developing aviation and space technology, avoid theoretical errors, and possibly also avoid accidents and catastrophes in aviation and space technology associated with the use of erroneous SRT formulas. The work provides reliable formulas that should be used instead of the corresponding erroneous SRT formulas.

The essence of the experiment (briefly)

The SRT concluded that if you observe a moving clock and compare its course with the course of a stationary clock, it turns out that moving clocks, according to observations, go slower than stationary ones. In order to confirm this conclusion of the STO, an experiment was conducted in which, using a radar, the clock rate was measured on twenty aircraft flying to and from the radar. Next, using classical methods of mathematical statistics, calculations were performed to confirm or refute a number of hypotheses, among which was the hypothesis that moving clocks, according to observations, run slower than stationary ones.

With a high level of significance, the hypothesis of the observed movement of a moving clock in accordance with SRT was discarded. In accordance with experimental data, it turned out that when observing a clock moving at a speed of v one second, according to the readings of these clocks on a stationary clock, not a second passes, but $(1 + v/c)$ seconds (more than one second) - when the clock is removed from the observer, and $(1 - v/c)$ seconds (less than one second) - when the clock approaches the observer.

The observed readings of a moving clock go *faster than* the observed readings of a stationary clock if the clock *approaches* the observer, and, on the contrary, the observed readings of a moving clock go slower than the observed readings of a stationary clock if the clock moves away from him. In other words, the observed course of the clock moving towards the observer is faster than the observed course of the observer's stationary clock, and, on the contrary, the observed course of the clock moving from the observer is slower than the observed course of the stationary clock.

The experiment showed that the above conclusion of SRT about the course of a moving clock is erroneous. The probability of an error in concluding that the SRT formula is unreliable is $2.56 \cdot 10^{-12}$. Such a low probability of error means that an error in drawing a conclusion about the unreliability of the SRT is practically impossible; an error is excluded.

7. Popular scientific presentation of the effect of deceleration and acceleration of the observed rate of clocks moving from or towards the observer

The popular science presentation of complex scientific ideas (or ideas that only seem complex) on the one hand popularizes science, and on the other hand, allows you to bring scientific truths to students and graduate students in an accessible form, who are still only at the foot of the mountain called science, but who are going to climb it.

In addition, popular science presentation is useful for scientists, doctors and candidates of science, who, due to the specialization of science, are specialists in branches of science that are far from the issues being presented, but who would benefit from becoming acquainted with them.

SRT is a science, and a rather complex science at that, which is studied starting from the 10th grade in the general education program. Therefore, the questions presented here may be of interest to, in fact, everyone.

7.1. Preliminary information about the observation of clocks remote from us

Everything we see around us - houses, streets, cars passing by, the Sun, Moon and stars, we see with the help of light, which is electromagnetic radiation perceived by our eyes.

Light from the objects we observe comes to us with a certain delay, equal to the time it takes the light to travel from the objects to our eyes.

When we admire a beautiful sunset, we see light that has been moving from the Sun for approximately 500 seconds (more than six minutes).

If there were a clock on the Sun with a huge dial covering the entire solar disk, which we could see with binoculars with tinted glasses (so as not to burn our eyes), then we would not see the current true time of this clock. Watching the clock on the Sun, we would see that this clock is 500 seconds behind our Earth clock!

Let's call "observed" clock readings, or "observed" clock time those clock readings that we can see with our own eyes, shoot on video with our smartphone, register with the help of video surveillance equipment.

Let us also call the "true" clock readings, or the "true" time of a clock, the time that this clock shows to an observer located next to it. In other words, the true time of a watch is the time it shows without taking into account the delay caused by the movement of light from the watch to our eyes.

It is very easy to determine the true time of a clock remote from us. The true time of the clock is determined by a simple formula:

$$\textit{True time} = \textit{Observed time} + \textit{Delay}$$

In this formula, Delay is the time interval during which a ray of light travels from the clock to our eyes.

Latency is also defined very simply:

$$\textit{Delay} = \frac{\textit{Distance to hours}}{\textit{Speed of light}}$$

That's why

$$\textit{True time} = \textit{Observed time} + \frac{\textit{Distance to hours}}{\textit{Speed of light}}$$

As we said, light from the Sun takes 500 seconds to reach our eyes.

If we, watching the clock on the Sun, saw the time "12:00:00" (12 noon), then at the same moment the true time on the Sun would be equal

$$\textit{True time} = 12:00:00 + 00:06:20 = 12:06:20$$

In this expression, "00:06:20" (6 minutes, 20 seconds) is the same 500 seconds that it takes for a ray of light to reach our eyes from the Sun.

So, at the moment when we would see "12:00:00" on the Sun, the true time on the Sun would be equal to "12:06:20" (6 minutes, 20 seconds more) (Fig. 3).

Fig 3. Hypothetically observing a clock with a huge dial on the Sun using binoculars, we will see the observed clock readings. Light from the Sun travels to the Earth in about 500 s. Therefore, the true readings of the clock on the Sun will be 500 s longer than the observed ones

It's simple. Remote clocks are always behind clocks near us (if the remote clocks are synchronized with our clocks in advance) by the delay time. Delay time is the time it takes for a ray of light to travel from the clock we observe to our eyes.

One of my acquaintances, a doctor of technical sciences, telling his students about the effect of delayed readings of remote clocks, says: "You see me as younger than I really am. And you see my ears are younger than my nose."

And this is true, because the distance from our eyes to the nose of our interlocutor is less than the distance to his ears. Therefore, the light from his nose reaches our eyes faster than the light from his ears.

This is similar to the fact that we see the stars that are more distant from us in the sky as younger than the stars that are closer to us.

a twenty-year-old attractive TV presenter was broadcasting live from a distant planet revolving around a star located 80 light-years away from us, then at the moment when we would see her twenty-year-old, in fact, she would already be a hundred-year-old old woman if she was still alive. Her real, true age is equal to the observed age (in the video report) plus the time of movement from a distant planet of electromagnetic waves, with the help of which the video report was transmitted.

If we were to look at a giant clock on the Moon, we would see that the lunar clock lags behind our Earth clock by about 1.27 seconds, assuming the Moon clock is synchronized with an accurate Earth clock (Figure 2). This is how long it takes light to travel from the Moon to the Earth.

Well, now let's imagine that a spaceship that has flown to the planet Neptune, using a radio channel, automatically transmits to us the readings of the ship's clock, and these readings are displayed on the clock display of the ship located on Earth.

The light and radio signal from the planet Neptune takes about four hours to reach Earth. This means that the observed clock readings of this spacecraft will be four hours behind the earth's clock! When our clock shows "12:00:00" (noon), the observed clock reading from the ship on Neptune that we will see on the display will be "08:00:00" (four hours less).

In the same way, if a video image of the ship's clock is broadcast from a ship, on Earth in this video image we will see that the clock readings we observe are four hours behind our clocks. At 12 noon according to earth clocks, we will see 8 o'clock in the morning on the video image transmitted from the planet Neptune.

It is important to note the fact that no matter how we observe the remote clock, the observed readings of these clocks will in all cases lag behind the true readings by the amount of delay determined in accordance with the above formula.

Our interim conclusions

1. Clocks distant from us, according to the readings we observe , *always lag* behind our clocks if they are synchronized with our clocks.
2. The amount of clock lag is directly proportional to the distance to the clock and inversely proportional to the speed of light.
3. The true time of the remote clock is equal to the sum of the observed clock reading and the amount of lag (delay time).
4. Let's not forget that the amount of lag in the observed readings of remote clocks is exactly equal to the delay time in the receipt of information about the clock readings to us, which is equal to the time it takes for a beam of light to travel from the clock to our eyes.

As soon as we understand well these, in general, simple information about the observed readings of clocks removed from our eyes, we will understand the essence of Einstein's childish error.

7.2. Watching a moving clock

Let us now consider what the observed clock will look like in the case of motion.

A child who catches up with his mother walking on the sidewalk understands that if you walk at the same speed as mother walks, you cannot catch up with her, and therefore you need to run faster than mother moves.

Any driver who is driving along the highway catching up with another car knows: in order to catch up with it, you need to drive faster, at a higher speed than the other car is driving (Fig. 4).

Fig 4. To catch up with the car ahead, you need to go faster than her

A similar situation occurs with the passage of hours. And even a schoolchild understands: if his watch a week ago was one hour behind the exact time, and now it is not behind, it means that during the week this clock *went faster* than the exact clock (Fig. 5). In other words, in order for a slow clock to catch up with a clock that is running accurately, it must hurry up and go faster.

Fig 5. If some clocks were behind a week ago, but are not behind now, it means that this week they were moving *faster than* the exact clock and thus caught up with them

If a car behind us drives at the same speed as us, it will never be able to catch up with our car.

If the lagging clock runs without speeding up, it will never be able to catch up with the accurate clock.

How to find the amount of lag in the observed readings of a remote clock

In astronomy, there is such a unit of measurement of distance as a light year. A light year is the distance that light travels in one year, traveling at a speed of about 300,000 km/s.

By analogy with the light year, we introduce the light second. We will call a *light second* the distance that light travels in one second.

According to this definition, the Moon is 1.27 light seconds from the Earth. The sun is 500 light seconds away from us.

It turns out that **the lag** in the observed readings of clocks distant from us, expressed in light seconds, is exactly **equal to the distance** to these clocks, expressed in light seconds (Fig. 6)!

The clock moving towards us, according to the observed readings, lags behind the true readings (in seconds) by the distance to the clock (in light seconds).

Fig 6. The lag of the observed clock readings in seconds is equal to the distance from the observer to the clock, expressed in light seconds

Thought experiment of observing a clock moving towards us

Now imagine that we are using a video broadcast to watch the clock readings of a spaceship located on the planet Neptune. As discussed above, light from the planet Neptune takes approximately four hours to reach Earth, so the observed spacecraft clock readings will be four hours behind our Earth clocks. When our clock shows "12:00:00" (noon), the observed clock reading from the ship on Neptune, which we will see on the board with the broadcast video image of the clock, will be equal to "08:00:00" (four hours less).

Suppose now that the ship from Neptune began to move towards the Earth. We will monitor the clock readings of this ship using a display that displays a video image of the clock transmitted from the ship.

When a spacecraft approaching the Earth displays on the clock display, it always lags behind the *delay time* required by the radio signal to convey information about the clock reading to the Earth. The delay time in seconds is equal to the distance to the ship in light seconds (Fig. 7). As the ship moves towards the Earth, the distance to it decreases, and at the same time, the lag of the ship's clock readings, which is equal to the delay time, *decreases* .

Fig 7. The spacecraft clock display on Earth *lags* by the time delay of the signal that carries the spacecraft clock readings to Earth

As the ship moves towards Earth, the distance from the ship to Earth decreases, which means that the delay in delivering clock readings to Earth also decreases; At the same time, the lag between the ship's clock and the earth's clock decreases (Fig. 8). This means that the readings on the clock of a ship moving towards Earth *go faster* than the readings on the earth's clock. In other words, the observed rate of passage of time of the clock approaching the Earth in the process of movement is higher than the true rate of passage of time of the earth's clock (Fig. 9).

We will circle this very important conclusion in a box.

Clocks moving towards the observer, according to their observed indications, move faster than the observer's stationary clock.

Fig 8. As the ship approaches the Earth, the delay in the delivery of clock readings to the Earth decreases and, at the same time, the delay between the ship's clock and the earth clock decreases. When the lag of the readings of the moving clock decreases, they catch up with the earth clock, which means they go faster

Fig 9. If the clock readings on the spacecraft approaching the Earth lagged behind the earth clock due to a delay in the signal about the ship's clock readings, and now they do not lag behind, then when moving towards the Earth, the ship's clock readings went faster than the exact clock and therefore caught up with them

The reason for the acceleration of the observed readings of the clock moving towards the observer is the delay in the receipt of information by the observer about the readings of the moving clock and their movement. In each subsequent second, the clock moving towards the observer turns out to be *closer* than in the previous second. Therefore, the amount of delay in the observer receiving information about the readings of a moving clock *decreases* as he moves (the readings of a moving clock lag behind the readings of a stationary clock less and less), and this causes the effect of *accelerating* the observed readings of a clock approaching the observer. Each subsequent second, according to the observed readings of the clock approaching the observer, passes *faster than* the previous second *due to the decrease in delays* in the receipt of information about the time of this clock.

The reason for the acceleration of the observed readings of clocks approaching the observer is the continuous decrease in the delay in the receipt of information by the observer about the readings of moving clocks as they move

In other words

The reason for the acceleration of the observed readings of clocks approaching the observer is the continuous decrease in the lag of these clocks, equal to the distance to the clock, expressed in light seconds.

Conclusion

If the clock was slow before, but now it is running accurately, it means that it *was speeding* up to eliminate the lag.

The clock readings of a spacecraft flying towards Earth *lag* while the signal about the readings of the ship's clock is being delivered to Earth.

After the ship landed on Earth, the readings of its clock were accurate, so during the flight, the readings of the ship's clock *accelerated* to eliminate the lag.

The case of spacecraft movement from the Earth

Let us consider the case of the spacecraft moving away from the Earth. As before, we will observe the readings of the ship's clock using the display of these clocks on Earth.

Obviously, if some clocks showed accurate time last week, but now they are behind, then this clock is running slower than accurate clocks (Fig. 10).

Fig 10. If some clocks were running exactly a week ago, but now they are behind, it means that this week they were running *slower than* an accurate clock.

When a spacecraft is in flight at some distance from the Earth, the clock signal from the spacecraft will arrive to the ground with a delay (delay). The further the ship moves away from the Earth, the greater the delay in the arrival of the signal with the clock readings, the more the readings of the ship's clock on Earth will lag behind.

But if so, this means that the readings on the clock of the ship, which is moving away from the Earth, go slower than the exact clock (Fig. 11).

Fig 11. At the time of the launch of the spacecraft, the clock was accurate. As the ship flies away from Earth, due to the increasing signal delay, the ship's clock display lags further and further behind. This means that the clock readings of the receding ship are *slower than* the exact clocks.

Thus, when the clock moves away from the observer, the *observed* course of time of this clock is always slower than the motion of the observer's stationary clock. Clocks moving away from the observer, according to their observed readings, *run slower* than the observer's stationary clock.

Let's frame this conclusion.

Clocks moving away from the observer, according to their observed readings, run slower than the observer's stationary clock.

The reason for the slowdown in the observed readings of the clock moving from the observer is the delay in the receipt of information by the observer about the readings of the moving clock and their movement. In each next second, the clock moving from the observer is further away than in the previous second. Therefore, the amount of delay in the observer receiving information about the readings of a moving clock increases as he moves (the readings of a moving clock lag behind the readings of a stationary clock more and more), and this causes the effect of a slowdown in the observed readings of a clock moving away from the observer. Each subsequent second, according to the observed readings of the clock moving away from the observer, passes *slower* (longer) than the previous second *due to increasing delays* in the receipt of information about the time of these clocks.

The reason for the slowdown in the course of the observed readings of clocks moving away from the observer is the continuous increase in the delay in the receipt of information by the observer about the readings of moving clocks as they move.

Conclusions

So, when the clock moves towards the observer, the observed readings of the approaching clock go *faster* than the readings of the stationary clock, but when the clock moves away from the observer, the observed readings of the receding clock go *slower* than the readings of the observer's stationary clock.

The reason for this effect is the delay in the receipt of information about the observed readings to the observer, as well as the movement of the clock relative to the observer.

Note that if the speed of light were infinitely large, then there would be no delay in the receipt of information about the progress of the ship's clock, and no one would notice any deviation of the observed readings of the moving clock from the readings of the stationary clock.

It can be noted that the observed time of a moving clock is always equal to the difference between the true time and the delay time in which the observer receives information about the readings of the moving clock:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Observed Time} &= \text{Real Time} - \text{Delay Time} = \\ &= \text{Real Time} - \frac{\text{Observed distance}}{\text{Speed of light}} \end{aligned}$$

7.3. Einstein's childhood mistake

Now we can talk about Einstein's childhood mistake.

In physics, there is one of the most famous and promoted theories, developed by the “genius of all times” Albert Einstein, which is called the special theory of relativity (STR).

Let's see what the special theory of relativity (SRT) says about the observed readings of a moving clock.

In A. Einstein's work “The Principle of Relativity and Its Consequences in Modern Physics” it is said: “*If you observe a clock* from a system in relation to which it is uniformly moving at a speed v , it will turn out that it *is moving* several $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ times *slower* than the same clock, stationary in relation to this system.

So, according to SRT, a moving clock, regardless of the direction of movement, according to their observed readings, *always goes slower* than a stationary clock. Let us emphasize that, according to SRT, both clocks moving away from the observer (which corresponds to the conclusions made above) and clocks approaching the observer (which contradicts the conclusions made) go slower.

That is, if the spacecraft approaches the Earth, then, in accordance with SRT, the observed clock readings of the ship moving towards the Earth *should go slower* than the earth's clock!

Nobel laureate R. Feynman, in his “Feynman Lectures on Physics,” expressed this position of the SRT about the slow motion of a moving clock as follows: “If you *watch* from the side how an astronaut (of a moving interplanetary spacecraft - author's note) lights a cigarette, it seems to you that that he does it *slower* than usual, although he himself believes that everything is happening at a normal pace. Therefore... instruments for measuring time (“*clocks*”) *must slow down*. In other words, when the clock on a spaceship counts down, in the opinion of the astronaut, 1 second, then in the opinion of an outside observer, $1/\sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ a second will pass.”

Whether the ship is approaching the observer or moving away from the observer makes absolutely no difference to SRT. You can replace “plus v ” with “minus v ” in the above formulas, which mathematically represents a change in the direction of movement to the opposite, the result remains unchanged. In all cases, the observed readings of the moving clock are slower than the stationary clock.

At the same time, in SRT the reason for the slowdown in the observed rate of a clock as it moves towards the observer is not explained.

7.4 . The discussion of the results

So, we see that the clocks moving towards the observer, according to their observed readings, go faster than the stationary clocks. And this is understandable: if a week ago the observed readings of the clock moving towards us lagged behind (due to a delay in the receipt of information about the progress of the clock), and today they do not lag behind (there is no delay), then the observed readings of these clocks in the process of movement went faster all week.

Previously, the clock was behind, but now it is not behind, which means that the clock has accelerated its pace in order to compensate for the lag. Any schoolchild will easily understand this. If the clock hands were slow before and now are not, it follows that the clock hands were somehow speeding up their movement in order to catch up with the exact time.

This is an obvious fact, which is confirmed by experiment.

Now let's compare this obvious fact with the statement of SRT, which has never been confirmed experimentally: when observing a moving clock (including one moving towards the observer), according to the observed readings, these clocks go slower than a stationary one.

Any student will understand: this conclusion of SRT is erroneous. Well, a clock moving towards an observer cannot slow down according to its observed readings! When moving away from the observer, they can, but when approaching him, no, they cannot!

Clocks approaching the observer, according to the observed indications, go faster than stationary clocks. It cannot be otherwise.

The position of SRT on the slowdown of the observed rate of clocks in the case of their approach to the observer is erroneous. This position contradicts the known laws of physics and the centuries-old experience of technical sciences.

7.5. Conclusions

After conducting a thought experiment of observing a clock moving on a spaceship, the following conclusions can be drawn.

The movement of a clock moving towards us is similar to the movement of a car catching up with our car on the road (Fig. 12).

Fig 12. The movement of a clock moving towards us is similar to the movement of a car on the road catching up with our car.

The car catching up with us lags behind us less and less, moving at a higher speed than us. Likewise, the clock approaching us lags less and less behind our clock, going faster than our clock.

Conclusion 1 . The clocks moving towards us, according to the observed readings, go faster than the stationary ones. The reason is the reduction in the lag of these clocks, which occurs as the distance to them decreases (the lag is directly proportional to the distance).

Conclusion 2 . Einstein made a childish mistake when he concluded that moving clocks, according to observed readings, *in all cases* (including when moving away from the observer) go slower than stationary ones. If the clock moves away from the observer, Einstein is right. However, when the clock moves towards the observer, this is erroneous.

7.6. Aberration theory - an alternative to SRT

For the first time in history, a Russian scientist, Doctor of Technical Sciences Alexander Petrovich Plyasovskikh, developed and experimentally confirmed an alternative theory to SRT. This theory is called the Theory of Aberration.

In accordance with this theory, clocks moving towards the observer according to their observed readings go faster than stationary clocks, and clocks moving away from the observer go slower than stationary clocks. At the same time, the true readings of the clock remain unchanged (the clock that has traveled does not lag behind the stationary ones). For this reason, in the Theory of Aberration there is no twin paradox and many other paradoxes that abound in SRT.

According to the Theory of Aberration, a person running towards us, before our eyes, ages faster than the same person running away from us. True, this kind of effect at earthly speeds is so

small that it is practically invisible to our eyes. In order to remain young in the eyes of her husband, a woman must fly away from him at the speed of light. True, when she returns to him, she will age very quickly before his eyes (this is, of course, a joke).

In the Theory of Aberration, bodies moving towards the observer are observed to be longer, and bodies moving away from the observer are observed to become shorter.

If a rotating plate approaches the observer, then the observed speed of its rotation becomes greater. If this plate moves away from the observer, then the observed speed of its rotation will slow down. In other words, if a wife throws a spinning rolling pin at her husband, the husband will see the rolling pin spinning faster than it actually is. If the wife throws a spinning rolling pin in the other direction, say, at someone else's dog, which stole the chicken cooked for a picnic, the husband will see that the rolling pin is spinning slower than it really is (this is again a joke).

If a picture of the Gioconda (Fig. 13, a) moves past us from left to right at a speed of 0.98 of the speed of light, and we have time to shoot it with a camera, then in the picture we will see the image shown in Fig. 13, b.

Fig 13. The picture moves relative to us from left to right at a speed of 0.98 of the speed of light: a) the true image of the picture; b) observed image. The image is published under a PD (Public Domain) license.

In the Theory of Aberration, a new, previously unknown physical law of aberration of physical quantities of a moving body was discovered, which is a significant event for science.

High practical significance of the theory of aberration

The theory of aberration has a high practical significance (value).

A number of patent-protected inventions have been made using the Theory of Aberration, which confirms its high practical significance for solving problems in astronautics and aviation. For example, using the Aberration Theory, a method has been developed for determining the location of objects using a global navigation satellite system using only two navigation satellites instead of four in the traditional method. This method will make it possible to create promising, more accurate, reliable and noise-resistant satellite navigation systems.

We are confident that with the help of the Theory of Aberration a large number of inventions and maybe even discoveries will be made that will be useful to humanity (in such areas as astronomy and cosmology, for example).

Where to get acquainted with the Theory of Aberration

You can get acquainted with the Theory of Aberration in the book “The Theory of Aberration. The first theory, alternative to the special theory of relativity: [Electronic resource]: monograph / A. P. Plyasovskikh - Moscow: Znanie-M, 2023. - 503 pp.” This book can be [purchased online at Litres](#).

Theory of Aberration is presented in the work “Plyasovskikh A.P. (2023). The theory of aberration is the first theory alternative to the special theory of relativity. Popular summary.” Zenodo . <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8150872>

The main conclusion of this work can be formulated as follows.

1. When the clock moves towards us, the distance to these clocks decreases, and at the same time, the lag of the observed readings of these clocks from our clocks also decreases; which means that the observed readings of clocks moving towards us go faster than stationary clocks.
2. Einstein made a mistake when he concluded that moving (including towards the observer) clocks, according to the observed readings, go slower than stationary ones.

8. Results and discussion

In this work it is proved that the observed time interval Δt_{obs} , counted according to the observed readings of the clock as it moves relative to the observer, is directly proportional to the true time interval Δt , counted according to the readings of the clock, located motionless next to the observer.

If the observed clock approaches the observer, the following relation holds:

$$\Delta t_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}, \quad (4a)$$

where v_{tr} is the true speed of the clock.

In accordance with this relationship, while one second will pass according to the stationary clock, the clock moving towards the observer, according to their observed readings, will report

$$\frac{1}{1 - \frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \text{seconds (more than a second).}$$

In other words, the clocks moving *towards the observer*, according to their observed readings, *go faster than* the stationary clocks.

The reason for the acceleration of the observed readings of the clock approaching the observer is *the continuous decrease* in the delay in the receipt of information about the readings of the moving clock to the observer as they move (continuous decrease in the lag of the observed readings of the clock moving towards the observer).

If the observed clock moves away from the observer, the following relation holds:

$$\Delta t_{obs} = \frac{\Delta t}{1 + \frac{v_{tr}}{c}}. \quad (4b)$$

In accordance with this, while one second will pass according to the stationary clock, the clock moving away from the observer, according to their observed readings, will report

$$\frac{1}{1+\frac{v_{tr}}{c}} \text{seconds (less than a second).}$$

In other words, the clocks moving *away from the observer*, according to their observed readings, *go slower than* the stationary clocks.

The reason for the slowdown in the progress of the observed readings of the clock moving away from the observer is the continuous *increase in the delay in the receipt* of information about the readings of the moving clock to the observer as they move (continuous increase in the lag of the observed readings of the clock moving away from the observer).

The effect of accelerating the observed rate of clocks as they move towards the observer and slowing down as they move away from the observer has been experimentally confirmed with a high level of significance.

The conclusion about the acceleration of the observed rate of clocks as they move towards the observer contradicts the SRT, according to which the observed rate of progress of a moving clock, regardless of the direction of movement, is less than the rate of motion of a stationary clock. According to SRT, a clock moving *towards the observer*, according to its observed readings, runs *slower than* the observer's stationary clock.

The reason for this is not explained in the SRT.

It has been theoretically proven and experimentally established that the STR conclusion about the slowdown in the observed readings of a clock moving towards the observer is erroneous. Formulas (4) are reliable.

In the section of this article with a popular scientific presentation of the fallacy of the conclusions of SRT about the deceleration of the observed progress of a moving clock as it moves towards the observer, the physical essence and reasons for the discussed effects of acceleration and deceleration of the observed progress of a moving clock as it moves towards the observer are simply and easily understood even by a schoolchild. and from him.

Conclusion

It is proved in the work that the clock moving towards the observer, according to their observed indications, *goes faster than* the stationary clock. *The reason for this is that the lag between the observed readings of the moving clock and the stationary clock continually decreases as it moves.*

The effect of accelerating the observed course of a clock moving towards the observer is proven and explained in works [1, 11-12] in at least three different ways. In addition, the presence of this effect was confirmed experimentally by scientists in St. Petersburg in 2022.

According to SRT, clocks moving towards the observer, according to their observed readings, *go slower than* stationary clocks. *The reason for this effect is not clearly explained in SRT.*

Thus, the provision of SRT on slowing down the observed rate of a moving clock, in the particular case of movement towards the observer, is clearly erroneous.

Please send comments and suggestions for work to:

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Bibliographic list

1. Plyasovskikh A.P. Theory of aberration. The first theory alternative to the special theory of relativity [Electronic resource]. – M.: Znanie-M, 2023. – 503 p. – [ISBN 978-5-00187-483-6](#)
2. Plyasovskikh A.P. and others. Experiment to measure the observed rate of movement of a moving clock // Avtomatika i program engineering. 2022, No. 4(42) URL: <http://www.jurnal.nips.ru/sites/default/files/AaSI-4-2022-4.pdf>
3. Plyasovskikh A.P. Experiment, the results of which contradict the special theory of relativity // Modern scientific research and innovation. 2023. No. 1 [Electronic resource]. URL: <https://web.snauka.ru/issues/2023/01/99461> (date of access: 01/14/2023).
4. Plyasovskikh AP Eshmuradov DE Experiment on measuring the observed rate of a moving clock // International Scientific Journal "Science and Innovation". Series A. Volume 2 Issue 3. 03/24/2023. — R. _ 169-188. URL: <http://scientists.uz/view.php?id=4089> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.776773>
5. Russian scientists disproved Einstein's special theory of relativity. <https://bloknot.ru/nauka/rossijskie-ucheny-e-oprovergli-spetsial-nuyu-teoriyu-otnositel-nosti-e-jnshtejna-1061085.html>
6. Russian scientists disproved Einstein's special theory of relativity <https://www.ecopravda.ru/nauka/rossijskie-ucheny-e-oprovergli-spetsialnuyu-teoriyu-otnositelnosti-ejnshtejna/>
7. Scientists from Russia disproved Einstein's special theory of relativity <https://actualnews.org/exclusive/458600-ucheny-iz-rossii-oprovergli-specialnuju-teoriju-otnositelnosti-jejnshtejna.html>
8. Russian scientists disproved Einstein's special theory of relativity On the day of Russian science https://lentafeed.com/@bloknot_rossii/26797/
9. Einstein's special theory of relativity was refuted in St. [Petersburg](#)
10. Scientists from the Russian Federation disproved Einstein's special theory of relativity This is reported by Rambler. <https://news.rambler.ru/science/50215073-ucheny-iz-rf-oprovergli-spetsialnuyu-teoriyu-otnositelnosti-eynshteyna/>
11. Plyasovskikh A.P. The law of aberration and its applications in navigation and air traffic control. — M.: Znanie-M, 2022. — 70 p. — [ISBN 978-5-00187-223-8](#)
12. Plyasovskikh, Alexander Petrovich. The theory of aberration - an alternative to the special theory of relativity: monograph / A. P. Plyasovskikh. - M.: Znanie-M, 2023. - 498 p. – ISBN 978-5-00187-635-9 .
13. Einstein A. On the special and general theory of relativity // Collection. scientific tr. - T. 1. - M., Science. - 1965. - P. 530-600.
14. Feynman lectures on physics. T. I (1–2) / Richard Feynman, Robert Leighton, Matthew Sands; [transl. from English. O. A. Khrustaleva, G. I. Kopylova, A. V. Efremova]. - M.: AST Publishing House, 2019. - 448 p.
15. Einstein A. The principle of relativity and its consequences in modern physics // Collection. scientific tr. - T. 1. - M., Science. - 1965. - P. 138-164.